

Attitudes Towards And Barriers To Research Among Medical Students In University Of Tabuk, Saudi Arabia

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 01 , 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 03 , 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Attitude, Barriers, Research, Medical Students, Saudi Arabia</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6612551</p>	<p><i>Background: Medical research is essential for the development of evidence-based practice and improving the quality of healthcare. We aimed to assess the attitude and barriers to research among medical students in University of Tabuk.</i></p> <p><i>Methods: This is a cross-sectional study conducted among 141 fifth and sixth year medical students in the medical College, University of Tabuk, Saudi Arabia (response rate 69.5%). A structured questionnaire was used to collect information regarding attitude towards research (14 questions), and barriers to research (12 questions. We used the Statistical Package for Social sciences for data analysis.</i></p> <p><i>Results: There were 141 medical students, their mean age (23.43±0.92) years, 52.3% were males, the attitude towards research was sub-optimal (27.1% students had good attitude towards research), more than half were average, while 21.2% had poor attitude. The most common barriers were lack of supervisors, time factors, and the demanding curriculum.</i></p> <p><i>Conclusion: The attitude of medical students towards undergraduate research was suboptimal, the most common barriers were lack of supervisors, time factors, and the demanding curriculum. Further studies regarding the attitudes of supervisors to research and barriers to supervision of students research are recommended.</i></p>

Introduction

Scientific research is one of the fundamental basic steps for the improvement of human society, thus any scientific movement needs to be supported by high quality research. The ability to generate and apply knowledge is essential for classifications of countries. The production and transfer of knowledge and the provision of a specialized service to the community all required scientific research undertaken by faculty and students (1). Medical students are required to develop research skills to improve the quality of healthcare and evidence-based practice, furthermore, getting involve in scientific research and publications while in medical school improve the chance of getting accepted in highly competitive residency training programs. Conducting a research is challenging for many students, however career advancement and interest in a specific field could be strong motivations. The perception that researchers are isolated from clinical practice, the availability of supervisors, and lack of time due to the highly demanding curricula are the most barriers for being involved in scientific research by medical students (2). Medical students participation in research activity is helpful in terms of gaining research skills thus, improving the patients care, a positive attitude towards research, adequate knowledge, and elimination of barriers to research are crucial for students participation. The observed recent decline in physician scientists has generated an increasing interest in programs for earlier students exposure to research (3). Previous literature documented that medical students are facing many barriers to conduct and publish scientific survey.

To our best of knowledge, no researchers have studies the attitude of medical students towards research and barriers to research in the Medical College, University of Tabuk, therefore this survey aimed to assess the attitude and barriers to research among medical students in Tabuk University.

Subjects and Methods:

This is a cross-sectional study conducted among the fifth and sixth year medical students (total number 150, response rate 94%) in Tabuk University, Saudi Arabia, the 5th and 6th medical students were selected because they are the mostly involved in research activity. The research was conducted during the year 2021 (January-April). A structured questionnaire based on the previous literature was used to collect the attitude (fourteen questions) and barriers (twelve questions). The attitude questions ask about the importance of research, and if conducting research in the college should be obligatory. In addition, if research methodology must be a part of the curriculum. The question was extended to include the impact of research conduction during medical school and whether the student's record should be an important criterion for acceptance in residency. Also, if research

conduction reinforces teamwork spirit and be a part of long-term career goals. Further questions are to anticipate a good understanding of research methodology and the impact of research on patient's outcome. Other questions asked if medical students should not be involved in research because undertaken research increases burden in already over-curriculum (heavy load – educational or clinical) medical student, if supervision is necessary and if students are encouraged by your seniors to get involved in any research activity. The barriers questions were: inadequate facilities for research, difficulty in topic selection and supervisors, inadequate support by mentors/assistant, lack of support, ethical approval delay, difficulty to access data, difficulty in drafting the proposal or contacting the research committee, the lengthy publication process, and lack of time and academic demands. Each question has five choices, strongly agree (5 marks), agree (4 marks), neutral (3 marks), disagree (2 marks), and strongly disagree (1 one mark). The total mark of attitude was calculated out of one hundred. The local ethical committee approved the research; the participants signed a written informed consent. The Statistical Package for Social sciences (SPSS, version 20, New York) was used for data analysis.

Results:

There were 141 medical students, their mean age (23.43 ± 0.92), 52.3% were males. The students acknowledge the importance of research (4.27 ± 1.21), and its role in improving the patients outcomes (4.22 ± 1.10), they agree that medical research should be a part of the curriculum (4.03 ± 1.31), however they scored 3.57 ± 1.42 regarding that participation should be compulsory. The students reported the lowest score when asked about whether they can plan and conduct research by their own (without supervision, 1.96 ± 1.13), followed by medical student should not be involved in medical research (2.49 ± 1.58). However, they felt that they are not encouraged by their seniors to get involved in any research activity (2.89 ± 1.50). The detailed students attitude towards research were shown in table 1. In the current study, the most important barrier to research was the difficulty in obtaining a research supervisor (3.68 ± 1.21), followed by academic demands (3.63 ± 1.34), inadequate support by mentors/assistant (3.57 ± 1.15), and inadequate facility for research (3.55 ± 1.37). The students scored the least in terms of unavailability of samples (3.09 ± 1.19), difficulty in contacting the research committee (3.17 ± 1.15), and difficulties in drafting the proposal (3.28 ± 1.19). Other barriers to research were depicted in table 2. It is interesting to note that only 27.6% students had good attitude towards research, more than half were average, while 21.3% had poor attitude. Table 3.

The current study showed that females have more positive attitude towards research (66.81 ± 20.08 vs. 54.96 ± 16.04) with significant statistical difference (P -value=0.003, CI=-19.66-4.03). Table 4

Table 1. Attitude regarding research among the 5th and 6th class medical students in the Medical College, University of Tabuk, KSA

Attitude, out of 5	Mean± SD
Research is important in medical field.	4.27±1.21
It is important to conduct research during medical school	3.71±1.41
Participation in research should be compulsory to all medical students.	3.57±1.42
Teaching research methodology should be part of the curriculum	4.03±1.31
Research conduction during medical school has positive impact on medical students	3.68±1.42
Research record should be an important criterion for acceptance in residency.	3.61±1.50
Research conduction reinforces teamwork spirit.	3.75±1.27
Research will be a part of long-term career goals.	3.91±1.27
Anticipate a good understanding of research methodology.	3.58±1.31
Patient outcome improves with continued medical research.	4.22±1.10
Medical student should not be involved in medical research.	2.49±1.58
Undertaken research increases burden in already over-curriculum (heavy load – educational or clinical) medical student.	3.20±1.36
Medical student can plan and conduct research project without supervision.	1.96±1.13

You encouraged by your seniors to get involved in any research activity.	2.89±1.50
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Table 2. Barriers to research among the 5th and 6th class medical College, University of Tabuk, KSA

Barrier	Mean ± SD
Inadequate facility for research	3.55±1.37
Difficulty in topic selection	3.32±1.33
Difficulty in obtaining a research supervisor	3.68±1.21
Inadequate support by mentors/assistant	3.57±1.15
Lack of rewarding and/or motivation	3.35±1.31
Difficulty obtaining approval for the study	3.48±1.24
Unavailability of the samples (or patients)	3.09±1.19
Difficulty in drafting the proposal	3.28±1.19
Difficulty in contacting the research committee	3.17±1.15
Publication is lengthy	3.34±1.07
Lack of time	3.51±1.45
Academic demands	3.63±1.34

Table 3. Attitude towards research among the study group

Character	No %
From 80-100%	39 (27.6%)
60-80%	72 (51.1%)
Less than 60%	30 (21.3%)

Table 4. Attitudes towards research among women and men medical students among the study group

Character	Male	Female	P-value	95%CI
Attitude	54.96±16.04	66.81±20.08	0.003	-19.66-4.03

Discussion:

The current study showed that medical student's attitude towards research was suboptimal, the most important barriers were difficulty in finding a supervisor, academic demands, inadequate facilities for research and inadequate support by mentors/assistant. A study published in Malaysia (4) among medical and dental students showed similar findings in terms of attitude and lack of facilities, however, the Malaysian study concluded that knowledge and skills as major barriers which was not the case in the current project. A plausible explanation is that, research methodology is included in the curriculum in our College. The current findings of difficulty in obtaining a research supervisor and lack of time were in line with a previous study conducted among medical students in Karachi, Pakistan (5), encouraging the faculty members and rewarding could be helpful regarding barriers to research. A study conducted in Syria (6) showed that students who are encouraged by their professors to participate in conducting and drafting scientific papers are more likely to participate in research projects. Lack of training in research was a major barrier in the Syrian study in contradiction to the present findings. Lack of time and undergraduate mentors are the commonest barriers to research in a previous study conducted among medical students in Alfaisal University College in Saudi Arabia (7) and were in similarity to the present observations. The lack of sufficient familiarity with research methods observed in Iran (8) was not present in the current study. The more positive attitude among female's students and inadequate facility for research, lack of interest by faculty or guide concluded in Taibah Medical College, Saudi Arabia (9) were in line with the current findings, while unavailability of the samples or patients was not. It is prudent to address and solve student's barriers to research by faculty staff and administrative personnel in order to improve the students participation in undergraduate research.

The study limitations were the small sample of the study sample, the reliance on a self-administrative questionnaire, and the study was conducted at a single College, so generalization cannot be insured.

Conclusion: The attitude of medical students towards undergraduate research was suboptimal, the most common barriers were lack of supervisors, time factors, and the demanding curriculum. Increasing the awareness regarding the undergraduate research among both the students and faculty members through rewards and regular meetings and conferences is highly recommended.

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